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Review Paper

Reproductive Toxicity of Rifampicin and Isoniazid on Male Reproductive System-A Review

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ABSTRACT

Mycobacterium tuberculosis is a primary cause of tuberculosis, a serious global infectious disease that mainly attacks the lungs. Conventional therapy depends on first, line drugs like Rifampicin Isoniazid Ethambutol, and Pyrazinamide. Despite these medications being extremely effective in infection control, extended therapy has been linked to a variety of side effects, including reproductive toxicity. Several research using animals demonstrates that antitubercular drugs first induce oxidative stress and then cause DNA fragmentation, structural changes, and hormonal disruption in the reproductive testis. Such alterations result in a reduction in sperm number, movement disorder, morphological anomalies, and ultimate fertility decline. Oxidative changes including rise lipid peroxidation levels and fall antioxidant actions through glutathione and respective enzymes are the main reasons of these manifestations. In sum, this review study indicates that the extended course of antitubercular drugs treatment could have negative effects on male reproductive function and should be investigated in further studies and development of new therapies, which can protect from the toxicity of these drugs

INTRODUCTION

Mycobacterium tuberculosis is the bacterium that causes tuberculosis (TB), which is still one of the most serious infectious diseases in the world. Although it can affect other organs, the most prevalent type of tuberculosis is pulmonary tuberculosis because the pathogen prefers lung

tissue [1]. The infection is mainly spread by airborne droplets produced by speaking, sneezing, or coughing, which makes it easy for the infection to spread in crowded areas. After exposure, people may develop latent or active tuberculosis; over the course of a lifetime, 10% of latent infections progress to active disease. Microbiological cultures, the tuberculin skin test, and chest

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radiography are among the methods that are commonly used in the diagnosis process [1]. Ethambutol, pyrazinamide, isoniazid, and rifampicin are the standard first-line drugs for the treatment of susceptible tuberculosis. These drugs are approved by the Food and Drug Administration [2]. Depending on whether the infection is passive or active, treatment regimen varies: Active tuberculosis requires prolonged multidrug therapy [3]. The rise of extensive drug resistant forms of tuberculosis, which is resistant to fluoroquinolones and second, line injectable agents, and multidrug, resistant tuberculosis which is resistant to isoniazid and rifampicin, poses a major threat to the international community's health [4][5]. These resistant strains are a major cause of death, treatment becomes more complicated, and the period of therapy is extended. Among the different tuberculosis treatments, the very efficient bactericidal rifampicin and isoniazid still remain the cornerstones of the therapy [6]. *M. tuberculosis* besides that has intrinsic resistance mechanisms which interfere with the effectiveness of antibiotics [7]. First, line ATDs are really potent; however, their long, term use is related to the development of various toxicities. Importantly, a study has demonstrated that co-administration of ethambutol, isoniazid, rifampicin, and pyrazinamide leads to oxidative stress, which in turn could disrupt male fertility through elevation in malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and reduction in glutathione (GSH) and sulfhydryl (SH) groups [8]. Considering these clinical challenges and safety issues, there is a growing need to reconsider current antitubercular regimens, thoroughly assess drug, induced toxicities, and explore possibilities for intervention to ensure better treatment results. Rifampicin, commonly referred to as rifampin, is a broad-spectrum antibiotic that exhibits strong antibacterial activity against a variety of gram-positive cocci, such as *Mycobacteria* and *Clostridium difficile*. It also acts against some

gram, negative organisms like *Neisseria meningitidis*, *Haemophilus influenzae* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* [9]. As a result of its potent sterilizing action and its ability to significantly reduce treatment duration, rifampicin, which was discovered in 1965, continues to be one of the key drugs in the treatment of tuberculosis [10]. Moreover, rifampicin off-label is also used to treat leprosy and, positive infections such as osteomyelitis, severe gram, anthrax, endocarditis, and brain abscesses. It is also a prevention treatment for those who have *Haemophilus influenzae* and could infect children younger than four [9]. Through the reversible inhibition of DNA, dependent RNA polymerase, rifampicin impairs bacterial RNA transcription and thus protein synthesis, which is the mechanism of its antimicrobial effect [11]. Another significant first-line medications used to treat *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infections is isoniazid (INH). Its continued use makes it a major component in the combating of tuberculosis. Isoniazid has been in use since 1952, and since then, it has played a major role in both latent and active tuberculosis infection treatment. The compound is a very powerful synthetic antimicrobial agent [12]. Isoniazid, as a pro, drug, is converted to its active form by the mycobacterial catalase-peroxidase enzyme (KatG), and its active metabolite then inhibits the synthesis of mycolic acids, which are the major components of the cell wall of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [11]. KatG is the enzyme catalase, peroxidase that causes tuberculosis. TB is killed as a result of the reactive species generated from this activation, which hindered the synthesis of mycolic acid, an essential component of the mycobacterial cell wall [13]. Spermatogenesis is a thoroughly studied process and the main fertility parameters-sperm count, morphology, motility, and fertilizing capacity can be accurately assessed under standardized conditions. When isoniazid, rifampicin,

ethambutol, and pyrazinamide were given together, the study showed that this treatment significantly decreased the fertility of male rats, increased the level of malondialdehyde and decreased the levels of glutathione (GSH), and protein-SH in testicular tissue and sperm [14]. This review paper focuses on the possible reproductive toxicity of first-line antitubercular drugs and presents strong evidence for a focused review of the influence of antitubercular therapy on male reproductive health.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The author followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses or PRISMA. Both systematic reviews and meta-analyses are frequently published with recommendations. The literature review include both experimental and non-experimental studies using databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Science Direct and Google Scholar covering papers published between 1979 and 2025.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

i. Mode of Action and Genotoxic Mechanisms

Procarbazine caused rabbit spermatocytes and spermatids to undergo unscheduled DNA synthesis, which is a sign of DNA repair after genotoxic damage. On the other hand, isoniazid did not lead to DNA repair activity, thus, it had less genotoxic effect [15]. [16] studied that rifampicin activated the 17-hydroxylase enzyme of testicular microsomes, leading to an increase in androstenedione and testosterone secretion, and no change 17, 20-lyase or 17-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase. CYP2E1 was upregulated in rat testes exposure to isoniazid, thus initiating the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and formation of toxic metabolites which, consequently, led to DNA damage and disruption

of the sperm formation process [17]. Rifampicin could oppose the sperm damaging effects of imidacloprid via the improvement of CYP3A4 activity, thus, it should be noted that rifampicin plays a role as an inducer of enzyme in the testicular metabolism [18].

ii. Histopathological Study

[19] observed that the reproductive organs had degenerated and epididymal sperm showed abnormalities in rats that were treated with rifampicin. The spermatogenic epithelium was damaged, there was more DNA fragmentation, and the fertilizing capacity was reduced after the administration of ethambutol, isoniazid, rifampicin, and pyrazinamide together [14]. The epithelial height was reduced, there was loss of germ cells and the seminiferous tubules became irregular after the treatment with rifampicin and isoniazid, which were almost completely restored by bee pollen supplementation [8]. [20] in his findings observed that the testicular histoarchitecture changed and DNA was broken in rats treated with INH, RIF, and PZA. The findings that rifampicin induced a deterioration of sperm chromatin integrity that was dependent on dose and time [21]. Testicular degeneration as very severe-the spermatogenic epithelium became thin, germ cells were disorganized and sperm was absent in the lumen as a result of exposure to isoniazid and rifampicin [22].

iii. Oxidative Stress and Antioxidant Imbalance

Anti-TB drug exposure caused a marked increase in thio-barbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) and decrease in glutathione and protein SH, groups in testis and sperm of rats [14]. After combined anti-TB drug therapy showed an 82% increase in testicular lipid peroxidation (LPO) along with drastic reductions in the activities of superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione

peroxidase (GPx), and content of reduced glutathione (GSH) [23]. Increased lipid peroxidation (LPO) and depletion of antioxidant defense in the testes of treated rats [20]. The levels of antioxidant enzymes (SOD, GPx, catalase, GST) were significantly increased and the level of malondialdehyde was lowered in case of bee pollen co-administration [8]. Increased catalase activity after RIPE administration that might represent a compensatory antioxidant response to oxidative insult [24].

iv. Biochemical and Enzymatic Study

[16] studied that rifampicin treatment in rats led to a significant upregulation of progesterone metabolism to androstenedione and testosterone which is consistent with the stimulation of hydroxylase enzyme activity. After the administration of isoniazid an increase in the activity of p, nitrophenol hydroxylase and GST activation [17]. The treatment of male rats with a combination of anti-TB drugs led to a decrease in total protein levels in the liver [24]. The great decreases in enzymatic antioxidants and metabolic efficiency were seen in rats treated with anti-TB

drugs [23]. On the other hand, there were significant reductions in testicular weight and organo-somatic indices, which are indicators of metabolic and structural damage [25].

v. Hormonal Changes and Fertility

[17] observed the serum testosterone levels decreased by 1.62 times after isoniazid exposure and this was accompanied by sperm counts drop and fertility loss. The testosterone, luteinizing hormone and follicle, stimulating hormone levels were significantly lowered in male rats treated with RIPE while prolactin levels moderately increased [24]. Lower testosterone and luteinizing hormone levels in parallel to reduced sperm count and motility [23]. First, line anti-TB drug, treated mice showed a decrease in sperm number, motility, nuclear maturity, and an increase in DNA damage [26]. Decreased sperm motility and impaired fertility potential as a result of rifampicin exposure [21]. [22] studied that the sperm count and sperm motility were reduced by 50.38% and 47.02%, respectively, in isoniazid and rifampicin treated mice.

Table 1- Toxic effects of rifampicin and isoniazid on male reproductive system

Sr. No.	Author and Year	Title	Dose and No. of Animals Used	Duration and Parameters	Findings	Remark
1.	Bürgin <i>et.al.</i> , (1979)	Assessment of DNA damage in germ cells of male rabbits treated with isoniazid and procarbazine	Rabbit 50 and 125 mg/kg dose of isoniazid	DNA repair synthesis analysis	Drug-induced DNA damage in these germ cells.	Isoniazid induced DNA damage and repair in germ cells.
2.	Nocke-Finck <i>et.al.</i> , (1981)	Effect of rifampicin on the biosynthesis of testosterone in rat testis	Male Wistar rat, 10mg/kg dose of Rifampicin	5 days Levels of progesterone, 17-hydroxyprogesterone, androstenedione, testosterone	Reduced progesterone, Androstenedione and testosterone increased, increased 17 α -	Rifampicin selectively affects steroid biosynthetic pathways.

					hydroxylase activity.	
3.	Awodele <i>et.al.</i> , (2010)	Modulatory activity of antioxidants against the toxicity of Rifampicin in vivo	40 Wistar albino rats therapeutic dose of rifampicin, rifampicin plus vitamin E, rifampicin and vitamin C.	3months Histopathology: liver, brain, reproductive organs	Hepatotoxicity, brain toxicity and impaired sperm quality	Rifampicin-induced multi-organ toxicity.
4.	Shayakh metova <i>et.al.</i> , (2012)	Damage of testicular cell macromolecules and reproductive capacity of male rats following co-administration of ethambutol, rifampicin, isoniazid and pyrazinamide	Wistar albino male (n=24) and female (n=48) rat rifampicin – 74.4 mg/kg b.w./day, isoniazid – 62 mg/kg b.w./day	4 months lipid peroxidation in testis and sperm, Fertilizing ability and fertility outcomes	Increased lipid peroxidation in testis & sperm, Increased DNA fragmentation, reduction in male fertility, fertilizing capacity	Oxidative stress, DNA damage, and severe fertility decline in male rats.
5.	Shayakh metova <i>et al.</i> , (2015)	Induction of CYP2E1 in testes of isoniazid-treated rats as possible cause of testicular disorders	-	Spermatogenesis histology, Sperm count, Serum testosterone	DNA damage, disturbances in spermatogenesis, and altered male fertility	Strong evidence of gonadotoxicity, leading to DNA damage
6.	Awodel <i>et.al.</i> , (2016)	The combined fixed-dose antituberculosis drugs alter some reproductive functions with oxidative stress involvement in Wistar rats	32 Wistar rat rifampicin, isoniazid 92.5 mg/m2 per body surface area	45 days Testicular histopathology, Sperm count, Serum testosterone, LH, FSH, prolactin	Sperm count decreased 27.3%, Serum testosterone, LH, FSH decreased	Significant reproductive toxicity, endocrine disruption, oxidative stress, and testicular vascular pathology.
7.	Kehinde <i>et.al.</i> (2016)	Biflavonoid fraction from <i>Garcinia kola</i> seed ameliorates hormonal imbalance and testicular oxidative damage by anti-tuberculosis drugs in Wistar rats	28 male Wistar rats, 4-Tabs=isoniazid 5 mg/kg, rifampicin 10 mg/kg, pyrazinamide 15 mg/kg and ethambutol 15 mg/kg in combination	3 times per week for 8 weeks, Body weight gain, Testicular weight, Testicular lipid peroxidation, Sperm count & motility, LH & testosterone	Decreased body weight and testicular weight, sperm count, motility, LH, testosterone, increased testicular lipid peroxidation.	Strong oxidative and reproductive toxicity.
8.	Bharti <i>et. al.</i> , (2017)	Modulatory activity of bee pollen against the	30 male rates 180 b/w, rifampicin 100 mg/kg b/w/day	Testicular histology and antioxidant changes	Increased antioxidant enzymes	Induced testicular damage.

		toxicity of antituberculosis drugs rifampicin and isoniazid in testis of Sprague Dawley rats	isoniazid 50 mg/kg/b/w/day		decreased MDA levels	
9.	Sharma <i>et.al.</i> , (2018)	<i>Berberis aristata</i> Ameliorates Testicular Toxicity Induced by Combination of First-Line Tuberculosis Drugs (Rifampicin + Isoniazid + Pyrazinamide) in Normal Wistar Rats	Isoniazid 30.85 mg/kg + rifampicin 61.7 mg/kg + pyrazinamide 132.65 mg/kg	28 days Lipid peroxidation, catalase, DNA fragmentation Histopathology of testes	Increased DNA fragmentation, Lipid peroxidation, decreased antioxidants, reduced germ cells, disrupted tubules.	Marked oxidative testicular damage
10.	Rao <i>et.al.</i> , (2020)	Exposure to first line anti-tuberculosis drugs in prepubertal age reduces the quality and functional competence of spermatozoa and oocytes in Swiss albino mice	Male and Female Swiss albino mice	4 weeks Epididymal sperm count, Sperm motility, Nuclear maturity, Sperm head abnormalities, Mitochondrial integrity, DNA damage	Decreased sperm number, motility, increased sperm head abnormalities mitochondria-l damage, DNA fragmentatio-n.	Marked sperm toxicity, DNA damage, and impaired male reproductiv-e potential.
11.	Al-Asady <i>et. al.</i> , (2021)	Impacts administration of Rifampicin on sperm DNA integrity and Male Reproductive System parameters in rats	42 male adult rat 27mg/kg/day or 54mg/kg/day rifampicin	14 days or 28 days respectively Sperm motility, DNA staining, Fertility potential	Decreased Sperm motility, increased sperm DNA staining, chromatin disruption, reduced male fertility	Time-dependent reproductive toxicity, affecting chromatin structure and fertility
12.	Zhao <i>et.al.</i> , (2021)	Spermiogenesis toxicity of imidacloprid in rats, possible role of CYP3A4	30 mature male rats imidacloprid (dose as above) + rifampicin (CYP3A4 inducer)	90 days Sperm concentration and morphology, Testosterone, estradiol, gonadotropins, CYP3A4 activity, Testicular histopathology	Abnormal sperm morphology, decreased sperm concentration, testosterone, estradiol and gonadotropins unchanged, Testicular damage, IMI persisted in tissues, inhibited CYP3A4.	Low-dose imidacloprid impaired sperm parameters via CYP3A4 inhibition; rifampicin reversed effects

13.	Bakare <i>et.al.</i> , (2022)	The first-line antituberculosis drugs, and their fixed-dose combination induced abnormal sperm morphology and histological lesions in the testicular cells of male mice	Male Swiss albino mice 2.5, 5.0, 10, and 20 mg/kg bw of rifampicin, 1.25, 2.5, 5.0 and 10 mg/kg bw of isoniazid and 7, 14, 28 and 56 mg/kg bw of FDC corresponding respectively.	Exposed for 5 consecutive days abnormal spermatozoa, Testicular weight	Increased abnormal spermatozoa, decrease in testicular weight, Organosomatic indices	Greater induction of sperm abnormalities, drugs modulate toxicity.
14.	Song <i>et.al.</i> (2025)	<i>Lycium barbarum</i> and <i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i> synergistically protect against anti-tuberculosis drug-induced male reproductive injury via gut microbiota-independent pathways in mice	40mice Ultrapure water + rifampicin+isoniazid daily, Wolfberry decoction 3 h before rifampicin, + isoniazid Levocarnitine 3 h before rifampicin, + isoniazid	21 days Sperm count, Sperm motility, Testicular histopathology	Decreased sperm count and motility, reduced germinal cell layers, thin spermatogenic epithelium, disorganized seminiferous epithelium, no sperm in lumen	Severe impairment of spermatogenesis

CONCLUSION

This review put forward one of the limitations of the first line of antitubercular drugs, mainly Rifampicin and Isoniazid, in the treatment of Tuberculosis caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is the detrimental effect on male reproductive health. Studies shows that continual use of these medications can upset the oxidants, antioxidants equilibrium, increase lipid peroxidation, and lower antioxidant factors in testes tissues. Molecular alterations of this nature could be the reason for physical changes in testes, such as the reduction in the size of seminiferous tubules, germ cells death, and spermatogenesis halt. Moreover, hormones changes including testosterone, Luteinizing Hormone, and Follicle Stimulating Hormone drop result in lower sperm count, motility, and fertility potential overall. Though antitubercular drugs are the only means of tuberculosis infection control, these studies shows

that male reproductive system is damaged in long term treatment circumstances. Additional research is necessary to disclose the routes of drug, induced reproductive toxicity and to develop drug strategies that could prevent such side effects without hampering the mechanisms that result in tuberculosis cure.

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DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflicts of interest.

Authors Contribution

Sakshi Tembhare and Yamini Makarwar conducted the literature search which was verified by Urmila Jiwantare and Varsha Dhurvey. Sakshi Tembhare wrote the first draft of the manuscript, while Yamini Makarwar and Shikha Sethiya critically corrected it. All of them agreed on the final manuscript.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not Applicable

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